

Experimental Study on RC Columns Strengthened with CFRP and Steel Plates under Axial Compression

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ABSTRACT

FRP strengthening is an effective solution for repairing and strengthening RC columns. Researchers in the past investigated the performance of the externally bonded (EB) FRP-confined columns. However, the data is only limited to columns of smaller size. Furthermore, the confinement of FRP is less effective for columns having aspect ratios greater than two. Hence, this study evaluates different strengthening configurations for columns with higher aspect ratios. A total of six RC columns of size 150 mm x 450 mm and 1500 mm in length are cast, strengthened using four configurations under axial compression. The chosen strengthening configurations include (i) confinement with externally bonded-CFRP fabric, (ii) near-surface mounting with CFRP laminates, (iii) steel plate anchored with bolts and (iv) steel plate anchoring along with CFRP confinement. The influence of these strengthening configurations on their axial capacity and ductility is experimentally evaluated. Results demonstrate that the hybrid strengthening configurations performed better than the others for columns with aspect ratio of three.

KEYWORDS

RC Columns; Aspect ratio; Axial compression; EB confinement; NSM; steel plates; Hybrid strengthening; Anchor bolts.

INTRODUCTION

Maintenance, repair and strengthening of civil infrastructural elements are essential for their safety performance. There are several situations where repair and strengthening of the existing structures shall be employed, such as increasing load demands due to changes in design code provisions, changes in usage, and addressing deterioration of structures due to corrosion. Presence of structural deficiency because of errors in design and construction. Damages in the structures because of natural disasters.

To address these issues, there are different strengthening methods available. FRP confinement is easy to implement out of all possible strengthening methods and can increase the axial compression capacity without adding any dead loads to the structure (Balla et al., 2023). As a result, researchers focused on this area (Fan et al., 2023; Lam & Teng, 2003). In FRP strengthening of columns, most of the experimental data is limited to small cross sections with only externally bonded CFRP systems (Abbasnia & Ziaadiny, 2015). The main purpose of the CFRP strengthening system is to confine the concrete in tri-axial state so that the ultimate strain and stress get enhanced (Toutanji et al., 2010). However, the confining action of CFRP jackets works effectively only on circular columns due to the effective confinement of the column around the section.

Figure 1. CFRP Confinement effect in different cross-sections

In case of square and rectangular sections, the confinement effect reduces (de Diego et al., 2022; Rocca, 2007). It follows a parabolic profile, as shown in Figure 1. The reduction in the confinement prevails more in the wall-type columns in which the aspect ratio (larger to smaller) of the cross-section is more than two (Vuggumudi & Alagusundaramoorthy, 2018). Researchers experimentally evaluated the influence of the aspect ratio of the column cross-section on its CFRP confinement. In this study, the maximum considered aspect ratio was three, with a base size of 150 mm. This concluded that the ultimate compressive strength and axial strains decrease as the aspect ratio of the column section increases (Malleswara Rao & Prakash, 2021).

Researchers proposed different strengthening techniques to improve the confinement effectiveness of these wall-type columns (Chellapandian et al., 2017). Different combinations with externally bonded, near-surface mounted laminates and a hybrid strengthening system have been tried. Results demonstrated that the hybrid strengthening system (NSM_L + EB) improved the wall-type column's performance compared to other strengthening systems. Zeng et al., (2018) studied the effect of corner radius on the confinement of wall-type cross-sections 435×290 mm. In this experimental study, different corner radii (25mm, 45mm, 65mm) were introduced in the section, and their effectiveness was evaluated. The ultimate strength and strain were found to increase with an increase in corner radius (Wang & Wu, 2008). Researchers evaluated the effect of fiber anchors on the strength improvement of the wall-type column with cross-section aspect ratio more than three. The results demonstrated that the fiber anchors on the larger side surface effectively restrain the concrete from bulging out, thereby increasing the confinement area and ultimate strength (Hwee Tan, 2002; Triantafillou et al., 2016).

RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION

It is observed that few experimental studies are available on wall-type columns with an aspect ratio of more than two. Moreover, most of these experimental studies were focused only on externally wrapped CFRP strengthening systems (De Luca et al., n.d.; Wu & Wei, 2010). Therefore, further research is required to expand the experimental database on wall-type columns strengthened with novel strengthening techniques. The main objective of this research study is to evaluate the performance of wall-type columns of cross-section $150\text{mm} \times 450\text{mm}$ with different strengthening configurations. The employed strengthening configurations in this study are externally wrapped CFRP system (EB), Near-surface mounted CFRP laminate system and Hybrid (EB+ NSM) system. The NSM laminates act as extra longitudinal reinforcement, increasing the column's strength. In addition, a novel strengthening method, near surface-mounted steel plates with anchor bolts, was introduced. The steel plates help to improve the columns' stiffness and strength under combinations of bending and compression loads. The main contribution of this study is to understand the performance of near-surface mounted steel plates with anchor bolt strengthening methods and other existing methods.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

Material properties

The concrete mix was designed as per IS: 10262 - 2019 to achieve the target 28-day cylinder ($150 \text{ mm} \times 300 \text{ mm}$) strength of 25 MPa. The average cylinder strength of the concrete at the testing age was 28 MPa. Fe500 grade steel was used as a longitudinal (12mm) and transverse reinforcement (8mm) in all the columns. The percentage of longitudinal steel reinforcement was 1%, and the volumetric percentage of transverse reinforcement was 0.67%. The CFRP, steel plates and anchor bolt material properties are mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: Material Properties

S. No	Material	Modulus of Elasticity (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
1	Reinforcing steel	200000	500
2	CFRP Hand lay-up – 600 GSM	85000	1160
3	CFRP Pultruded laminate – 1.4 mm	158000	2900
4	Anchor bolts – M10	200000	400 *Ultimate
5	Steel plate – E250	200000	250

Details of test specimens

A total of six RC columns were cast with dimensions of 150mm×450mm of length 1500mm. These columns were reinforced with six bars of 12 mm diameter as the longitudinal reinforcement, and 8 mm diameter were used as the tie bars. The tie bars were spaced with a centre-to-centre spacing of 75 mm at the bottom and top up to 300mm to prevent end failure due to stress concentration. In other zones, 200 mm spacing of ties was adopted. All the columns were water cured with gunny bags for 28 days.

The adopted strengthening configurations in this study were externally wrapped with CFRP fabric (EW), Near-surface mounted laminates (NSM_L), Near-surface mounted steel plates with anchor bolts (NSM_S_AB), Near-surface mounted with externally wrapped with CFRP fabric (NSM_L + EW). Near-surface mounted steel plates with anchor bolts and external CFRP fabric wrap (NSM_S_AB + EW). The corners of columns with an externally wrapped system were ground with a 25mm radius. The complete sectional details of the adopted strengthening configurations are mentioned in Table 2.

Table 2: Details of test specimens

Test Configuration	Details
Control	
Externally wrapped (EW)	
Near-surface mounted laminates (NSM_L)	
Near-surface mounted laminates with externally wrapped (NSM_L + EW)	

<p>Near surface-mounted steel plates with anchor bolts (NSM_SP_AB)</p>	
<p>Near Surface Mounted Steel Plate with Anchor Bolts with externally wrapped (NSM_SP_AB +EW)</p>	

Strengthening procedure

Externally wrapped columns (EW),

Initially, a corner radius of 25 mm was made in all four corners. After that, a primer base was applied to the whole surface of the column. After 24 hours of curing, an epoxy resin was prepared using a hardener and base by mixing them in mentioned proportions. The epoxy resin was slowly applied to the surface of the concrete. In the next step, a single layer of CFRP fabric was slowly placed on the surface of the concrete using a hand lay-up process. An overlap of 50mm was maintained between two layers in the longitudinal direction, and 100 mm was in the transverse direction. Finally, the epoxy resin was applied on top of the CFRP fabric.

Near-surface mounted laminates (NSM_L)

Eight grooves of size 21 mm × 23 mm were initially made in the concrete columns. Further, a primer base was applied to all the grooves. Laminate epoxy resin was poured into the grooves before placing the laminates. Finally, five numbers of pultruded laminates of size 15mm×1.4mm were slowly pushed into each groove, and extra epoxy was removed and levelled.

Near-surface mounted steel plates with anchor bolts (NSM_S_AB)

In this strengthening method, six grooves were initially made of 55 mm × 15 mm. Further, holes were made in the grooves with a depth of 90 mm and a diameter of 12 mm using a drilling machine. After that, the holes were cleaned, and a primer base was applied to the grooves. After one day of curing primer, A chemical adhesive was inserted in the bolt holes. Meanwhile, laminate epoxy resin was applied to the grooves and steel plates. After that, steel plates of dimension 50 mm × 12mm of length 1480mm were slowly pushed into the grooves and the anchor bolts were inserted into the bolt holes from the top of the steel plates by rotating them clockwise. Finally, after 24 Hrs of curing, the nuts were tightened to the anchor bolts and the extra length of bolts was cut using a steel cutting machine.

Near-surface mounted laminates + externally wrapped CFRP (NSM_L+EW)

Near-surface mounted laminates (NSM_L) strengthening scheme was applied first. Further, the column was strengthened using the externally wrapped scheme as previously mentioned.

Near-surface mounted steel plates with anchor bolts + externally wrapped CFRP (NSM_S_AB + EW)

Near-surface mounted steel plate with anchor bolts (NSM_S_AB) strengthening scheme was applied initially. Further, the column was strengthened using the externally wrapped scheme mentioned in this paper.

Test setup

a servo-controlled compression testing machine with a capacity of 3,000 kN was used to evaluate the behaviour of the control and strengthened RC columns under concentric compression. A total of six linear variable displacement transducers (LVDTs) were installed at the midsection of the column, as shown in Figure 2. Four LVDTs were installed along the direction of the applied load to measure axial deformation. The remaining two were installed to measure lateral deformation at the mid-section of the column. Moreover, all the LVDTs were connected to the Data Acquisition System (DAQ). A 10 mm thick cementitious grout material was applied on the top and bottom ends of the column to ensure a level surface. The steel caps were attached at both ends of the column to avoid failure due to stress concentration. An average deformation of LVDTs was taken as the axial deformation to compare the results.

Displacement control loading type was adopted in all the tests with a 2mm/minute loading rate. An initial preload of 70 kN was applied three times to remove the slack in the system. The loading was stopped after the post-peak load reached 70 % of the peak load.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

All the tested columns, peak load, axial deformation at peak and failure load, and percentage increase in peak load are mentioned in Table 3.

Table 3: Experimental results

S.No	Column Type	Peak Load (kN)	Percentage Increase in Peak Load w.r.to control	Axial Deformation at Peak Load (mm)	Axial Deformation at Failure (mm)
1	Control	1879	N.A	0.41	0.47
2	NSM_L	2002	6.54%	0.46	0.55
3	EW	2282	21.40%	0.66	0.73
4	NSM_L+EW	2488	32.40%	0.93	1.04
5	NSM_S_AB	2480	31.96%	0.34	0.49
6	NSM_S_AB + EW	2457	30.74%	0.40	0.82

Load vs Axial Deformation

Figure 3. Load vs. Axial deformation plots of all the tested columns

Figure 3 explains the behaviour of the considered strengthened configurations columns with respect to their axial loads and deformations. The observations from the results are as follows.

- The stiffness of the steel plate-strengthened columns is higher than the CFRP-strengthened columns.
- The peak load and axial deformation at failure are maximum for NSM_L + EW strengthened columns.

- The NSM_L strengthened column showed only a 6.54% increase in peak load with respect to the control column. In contrast, a 32.4% percentage of strength increment was observed in NSM_L + EW strengthened column.
- The least axial deformation was observed for NSM_S_AB strengthened column. Moreover, there is not much significant increase in its axial deformation with respect control column.

DISCUSSION ON FAILURE MODES

Figure 4. Failure pattern of tested strengthened columns.

Figure 4. shows the failure pattern of the tested columns. The following observations are drawn from Figure 4.

- The control column failed at the mid-location. The failure was initiated by the longitudinal bar buckling, followed by the crushing and spalling of concrete. Moreover, the NSM_L column failed similarly to the control column.
- The Externally wrapped CFRP column failed by rupture of the CFRP wrap. However, in the case of the NSM_L + EW column, the failure was initiated by the buckling of CFRP laminates and crushing of concrete at the mid location. The CFRP laminates pushed the CFRP wrap outwards, thereby concrete getting crushed in that region.
- The failure pattern for steel plate strengthened columns differed from CFRP strengthened columns. Initially, failure was initiated at the end. Further, concrete crushing was observed around the plates along with the bending of plates.
- In the case of the NSM_S_AB + EW column, the failure was initiated by the bending of plates at the ends and followed by the rupture of the CFRP wrap.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions from this study are listed below.

- Confinement through external wrapping of the columns enhances the axial deformation at the peak load. Implicitly, it also improves the ductility of the columns. Moreover, it prevents the buckling of the longitudinal bar, thereby improving the column's load-carrying capacity.
- In the case of wall-type columns, NSM_L + EW strengthening configuration performed the best in improving the strength and ductility compared to other CFRP strengthening methods.
- The stiffness of steel plate-strengthened columns are more than the CFRP-strengthened columns. However, quality control shall be maintained to avoid delamination of steel plates or pull-out of the anchor bolts, resulting in reduced stiffness.
- NSM_S_AB and NSM_S_AB+EW columns reached almost the same strength as NSM_L + EW columns. Therefore, steel plate strengthening can replace CFRP strengthening for wall-type columns for better fire resistance. However, steel plate strengthening is more time-consuming and involves laborious work than CFRP strengthening.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge the Sanrachana Structural Strengthening Pvt. Ltd, India for the financial support of this experimental study.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.